

CMIP DROP IN SESSION REPORTS

Forcings

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1 Introduction

The CMIP Panel and WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP) are committed to open and inclusive communication, engagement, and co-creation with the CMIP community and wider end users and stakeholders during the CMIP7 planning process. A first step was to establish several Task Teams to support the design, scope, and definition of the next phase of CMIP and evolution of CMIP infrastructure and future operationalisation. Further information on the CMIP Task Teams can be found [here](#).

Further, a series of regular drop-in sessions was launched in early 2023, facilitated by the CMIP International Project Office (CMIP IPO), to cover key aspects of CMIP7 design and development and promote community feedback to the CMIP governance and Task Teams.

This report provides a summary of the first CMIP Forcings drop-in sessions held on 7 June 2023 across two timeslots (05:00 UTC and 16:00 UTC) to support equitable global participation.

These sessions aimed to facilitate community discussion on the development and use of forcing datasets. Each session was chaired by one of the CMIP Panel Co-chairs, [John Dunne](#) (GFDL/NOAA) and [Helene Hewitt](#) (Met Office) and led by the [Forcings Task Team](#) co-leads, [Paul Durack](#) (PCMDI/LLNL) and [Vaishali Naik](#) (GFDL/NOAA), with input from the wider task team membership. Participants were introduced to the task team's members and stakeholders together with the four core goals they are seeking to address. Further, feedback received in the recent CMIP Forcings Survey was outlined and how the task team is addressing issues raised here, to deliver to CMIP7 and tackle longer term scientific challenges, before opening the session for an interactive dialogue with participants.

Registration was open to anyone with an interest in CMIP forcing datasets through the wcrp-cmip.org website. There were 88 registered participants (of which 52 attended) across the two online sessions from across the globe representing data users, Model Intercomparison Projects (MIPs), forcing dataset providers, and particularly strong attendance from modelling centres.

2 Context

The CMIP Forcings Task Team

With 45% of respondents to the CMIP6 Community Survey expressing being dissatisfied or very dissatisfied, the delay in forcing data provision was the most commonly cited complaint. The ScenarioMIP forcing delays were reported as particularly problematic providing intense time pressure to meet the IPCC AR6 deadline. There was clear community consensus that there is a need for greater support and potential operationalisation of forcing datasets enabling more regular updates, temporal extensions and to ensure appropriate testing before these data are used by modelling centres.

The CMIP Forcings Task Team (Forcings TT) is focused on how the CMIP required forcing agents will need to broaden for CMIP7 and how the CMIP6 issues can be avoided or reduced. Climate forcings play a key role in the definition of forced and natural of climate change. As such, they are an integral part of the definition of historical, future scenario and idealised simulations. Due to the expanding complexities of Earth System Models to represent more processes explicitly, it is anticipated that required forcing inputs will need to broaden for CMIP7. As model configurations continue to target higher and higher spatial resolution, additional expansion of temporal and enhanced geographical resolutions may be required.

The team was selected during an open call process in late 2022 with members from both the forcing dataset providers and modelling centres. Full details on the task team can be found [here](#) and within the [session slide deck](#).

Core Goals

Following the first three meetings of the Climate Forcings Task Team, four core goals have been identified. These goals were approved by all Task Team members in April 2023:

- Evaluate and document the CMIP6-era forcing collection and identify issues, coverage gaps, or omissions through an open community survey.
- Identify forcings for current and next generation climate models in support of CMIP.
- Work with teams to identify, develop, document, and deliver an updated and expanded forcing collection to near real time.
- Coordinate with modelling groups to define and perform routine experiments for evaluation, generate simulations and gather feedback with these new forcing collections.

Full detail of the core goals can be viewed on the [website](#) or can be viewed in PDF form by [following this link](#).

3 Session format and programme

The sessions were designed to provide participants with information and, importantly, allow for open feedback and comment both from oral questions and using an online Padlet ideas board (see Annex A). A high-level update on CMIP7 planning from the CMIP Co-chairs, John Dunne, and Helene Hewitt, opened the session before the Forcings Task Team co-leads, Paul Durack and Vaishali Naik, led the participants through informational slides followed by regular opportunities for feedback and engagement through oral discussion and online Padlet contributions. The session slide deck is available [here](#) aligning with the session programme below:

Topic	Slide number	Presenters (05:00 UTC/15:00 UTC)
Welcome, housekeeping and instructions	1-3	Eleanor O'Rourke
Status of CMIP7 Planning	4-9	Helene Hewitt /John Dunne
Presentation: CMIP Forcings Task Team	10-16	Paul Durack/Vaishali Naik
Feedback: CMIP Forcings Task Team (5 mins)	17	Presenters and participants
Presentation: CMIP Forcings – lessons from CMIP6	18-24	Paul Durack/Vaishali Naik
Feedback: CMIP6 experience (10 mins)	25	Presenters and participants
Presentation: Timeline development for DECK and historical	26-28	Paul Durack/Vaishali Naik
Feedback: Timeline and new requirements (10 mins)	29	Presenters and participants
Presentation: Plans for testing	30-31	Paul Durack/Vaishali Naik
Feedback: Plans for testing (5 mins)	32	Presenters and participants
Presentation: Access, tools, documentation & engagement	33-37	Paul Durack
Feedback: Tools and communications (5 mins)	38	Presenters and participants
Next steps and thank you	39-41	Eleanor O'Rourke

4 Session summary

Both sessions provided a wealth of insightful questions, comments, and discussion both as oral questions and submitted onto the Padlet. The participant interactions will be carefully considered by the task team in its future activities and planning. Below the session content has been split into two sub-sections: a table of Q&A that has also been uploaded to the [CMIP website FAQs](#); and a list of specific requests raised for the Forcings TT to consider. The Padlet output can be viewed in Annex A.

Q&A

CMIP7 Status and timeline	
Question	Response
Can the DECK entry card be adapted for high resolution model participation?	<p>In CMIP6 some groups only participated to HighResMIP. CMIP7 will continue to take a pragmatic approach and the CMIP Panel along with the Strategic Ensemble Design Task Team are discussing this and do understand the need to deal with the resolution axis in a different way.</p> <p>It should be acknowledged that providing a historical simulation without a piControl coincident will limit data use (not being able to account for ocean heat content, ocean biogeochemistry drift is just one example), which is also true for omitting abrupt-4xCO2 (limits ECS estimation following the Gregory method).</p>
What constraints on the forcings timeline is imposed by IPCC AR7 deadlines, to the extent that they are known?	<p>The IPCC elections that will define the AR7 leadership take place in July 2023 (https://apps.ipcc.ch/fp/elections.php). Once the IPCC leadership is in place, their first job will be to define a timeline. Further information on the status of CMIP7 timeline planning can be found here.</p>
CMIP6 experience and issues	
Question	Response
Concern raised by some modelling groups around unusual fields in the scenarios forcing.	<p>The TT would ask for specific experiences to be shared particularly with problematic datasets. Everyone is encouraged to articulate issues and communicate with the TT (through cmip-ipo@esa.int) so these can be addressed before CMIP7. We aim to make preliminary data sets available earlier in the process this time around, providing more time for review and data checking. If your group would be interested in running preliminary data sets, please reach out as your feedback would be immensely valuable.</p>

CMIP6 experience and issues

<i>Question</i>	<i>Response</i>
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In CMIP6, some ScenarioMIP forcing data were provided at annual rather than decadal mean temporal resolution. This change was unexpected and there is a preference for time averaging consistency across the historical and scenario periods.

The change from historical on annual, and then scenarios at decadal is an inconsistency. Second inconsistency is interannual variability of forcings would not match free running coupled model. The IAMs only report emissions on a decadal timestep; however, we may be able to linearly interpolate down to annual at minimum and use more sophisticated solutions if we manage to develop them in time. Please reach out to cmip-ipo@esa.int with your preference.

The enhanced interannual variability of biomass burning emissions in the CMIP6 historical dataset has been raised as an issue (for example in [this paper](#)). Issues like this should be flagged to Forcings TT leads or to cmip-ipo@esa.int.

There have been quite a few papers highlighting the unintended consequences of having abrupt transitions in the mean or variability of certain forcings in CMIP6 on the global climate. Will there be more of an effort to homogenize these forcing datasets (e.g., pre-satellite vs post-satellite observations, historical vs future scenarios) in CMIP7 to avoid these types of discontinuities?

For CMIP6, there was limited forcing dataset evaluation, with the intense time pressures imposed by data preparation delays pushing priorities to delivery. As we are starting the data preparation process well in advance of a likely CMIP7 timeline, we hope to work through a far more comprehensive process of data evaluation, including homogenization across independent datasets. Once these are in place, we plan to test these with modelling groups to ensure that the simulation responses to new forcings match or improve those from CMIP6. In addition, the inconsistencies noted in the CMIP6 historical to ScenarioMIP transition will be a key focus area of evaluation in planned work

Will there be an attempt to specify natural emissions of short-lived gases and aerosols, unlike in CMIP6?

Currently we do not have natural emissions data providers identified. If natural emissions data were used in CMIP6, it would be useful to identify these contacts and see if they can be incorporated. It is difficult to separate what is "natural" and what is "anthropogenic", but for CH₄ etc, both can be quantified, with our SLCF data provider (CEDS) covering the anthropogenic part. For the biomass burning (BB) these are a mix, what aspect of fire is anthropogenic and what is natural? There have been ongoing conversations about how this would be done consistently when a land surface scheme includes a fire sub-model, where there may be very different behaviour between forced and internally simulated BB. The same question applies to e.g., forced vs. internally simulated methane wetland emissions (which many would consider natural but modified by feedbacks), and for mineral dust aerosols (naturally emitted from deserts plus anthropogenic contributions via feedbacks and anthropogenic land use).

Timeline and new requirements

<i>Question</i>	<i>Answer</i>
<p>Can CMIP6 forcing datasets be used if needed?</p>	<p>CMIP6 can be used but only up to 2014 and several issues with datasets have been identified. First updated or extended versions up to 2021 will be ready by mid-2024 with final CMIP7 versions extended to near real-time, where possible, in 2026. This timeline will allow for testing and evaluation.</p>
<p>What will the crossover date between historical and scenarios be for CMIP7?</p>	<p>This will be discussed further when we become clearer on the timeline and end deadline. Currently both a short term and longer term timeline development – current timeline status. Discussions are ongoing with ScenarioMIP to find a good year for harmonizing both historical and future forcings. Will ensure up to 2021 to include Covid but remains under discussion and will be progressed at ScenarioMIP workshop (20-22 June 2023).</p>
<p>When we will have a piControl forcing available. Will piControl forcing simply be derived from the 1850 historical forcing, and therefore piControl is defined (and from then on kept unchanged) once the historical forcing is defined? Community MIPs' simulation designs may depend on details of the piControl forcing. For PMIP, this dependence is very strong.</p>	<p>The piControl forcings are part of the DECK (and historical) forcing dataset delivery, which we expect in early 2024 (extended to at least 2021). Once these forcings are in place, we can revisit the experimental design protocol for piControl, in addition to interacting with PMIP colleagues to work toward consistency between the paleo and 1850- connection.</p>
<p>In the case of some forcings (e.g., solar, volcanic), I assume that the piControl forcings will not be simply the 1850 historical values, but rather some sort of multi-year mean?</p>	<p>Correct, the experimental design for CMIP6 was climatological values for the piControl (volcanic, average over 1850-2014 - see https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/input4mips/?institution_id=IACETH, and solar, average over 185001-187301 - see https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/input4mips/?institution_id=SOLARIS-HEPPA), which we may want to revisit once we have the next-generation forcings available and can assess their stability across the CMIP6 periods. We received some comments through the surveys about the CMIP6 piControl climatological volcanic forcing specification, and ongoing discussions are occurring within the TT and community.</p>

Timeline and new requirements

<i>Question</i>	<i>Answer</i>
<p>Can users get access to the individual forcings datasets as they are generated rather than waiting until they are all ready? A rolling delivery as some are already ready and do not need to wait until 2024.</p>	<p>We expect data to come online as they are ready, current timeline status will help answer. All data that has been validated through our testing will be available through input4MIPs - as real-time as the data are available, and published under the "CMIP6Plus" MIP era. We have our first CMIP6Plus era data, the PCMDI-AMIP-1-1-9 that was published last month and expect the new data to be made available as they are finalized. Importantly, we want to collect and test, so expect that numerous releases of each dataset may occur as validation, testing and feedback is addressed.</p>

To what extent is it now possible to operationalize the production of historical forcing data so that it is updated every year? This encompasses two classes of updates - single additional years that are continuous with the existing timeseries, and larger revisions that would periodically update an entire timeseries as a function of changing assumptions or new data. The impacts of COVID, or other unforeseen events (large biomass burning, volcanic eruptions, solar cycle updates, marine shipping emission cuts etc.) need to be assessed on timescales that much shorter than the typical CMIP cycle.

Single additional years: It would be great to append years to existing CMIP6 datasets; however, we are aware of several dataset issues that providers want to correct and there are also challenges with updating to account for Covid, during which measurement coverage was inconsistent.

Operational real time delivery: The workflow and data dependencies vary depending on the forcing dataset which means that there would be diversity in the definition of "real time". Some forcings may be updated/produced on an annual basis (e.g., GHGs) while others may not (e.g., land-use). It would be important to identify such dependencies and barriers to operational production of forcings. Additionally, a challenge is that currently forcing dataset providers in most cases are not specifically supported to produce these datasets. Therefore, we will need to determine a way to ensure adequate support is identified for this very important contribution to the CMIP project.

Timeline and new requirements

<i>Question</i>	<i>Answer</i>
<p>"Updates" (rather than "extensions") for the SLCF emissions are indicated on the <u>current timeline status</u>. Does this indicate that the whole historical timeseries will continue to change through 2026? If so, at what point will the "official" CMIP7 SLCF emissions be frozen? They cannot continue to change once model simulations need to start.</p>	<p>The CEDS SLCF database is a good example, in that it is constantly evolving. Whenever the data is written is the timestamp/version of the data, and even a week later, new observations may have been incorporated which means the timeseries would change. When we have a CMIP7 timeline, the forcing dataset collection will be set (just like we did in CMIP6), with no more "CMIP7" updates applied, unless of course issues are identified, which will be fixed, and a new collection identified etc.</p> <p>TT member (Steve Smith) does not recommend extending from 2015 (in the CMIP6 case). 2015 is the most uncertain year in the historical dataset and Steve strongly recommends, if there is a need to extend, to extend forward starting from a few years back e.g., 2010 (for CMIP6). The data at that point are more stable and you will get an extension that is much closer to the updated dataset. If the focus is on getting the most realistic behaviour for recent years, the suggestion is to jump back a bit farther, say 2000 or 1990, start with the previous simulation, and then merge from CMIP6 to the latest emissions over say a 10-year period. That way after that period the simulations would be using the most updated emissions (and with the gradual merge, there will not be significant transient artifacts). If models are interested in extending historical simulations with extensions of forcing data in the future that they should save restart data not just for the last CMIP historical year, but for 5 and 10 years before that so that updates to the last years of the forcing data can be used for a more accurate extension of historical model runs using updated historical data.</p>

Is there any information about whether the historical forcings will be extended back to 1750 for those groups who may want to try this?

This has been discussed in the Forcings TT as well as polling data providers in the survey to indicate the possibility to extend to 1750. Many datasets already extend back to 1750 (e.g., emissions, GHGs, volcanic SO₂ emissions and aerosol properties) and some new ones could be extended but not all can be extended (e.g., ozone). The consensus was that this request could come as part of a focused MIP activity and will then be evaluated to see how much work is needed.

Timeline and new requirements

<i>Question</i>	<i>Answer</i>
<p>For stratospheric aerosols in CMIP6 it was customised for every modelling group and concern as cannot update without someone in Europe doing this. What is the plan?</p>	<p>A new group is addressing this (Thomas Aubry and Anja Schmidt, members of the Forcings TT). The output will be a new dataset first addressing the SO₂ emissions and then the optical properties as we want to ensure consistency between these. Several modelling groups do need band dependent information for optical properties so need to determine if this new provider is able to provide this and sustain ongoing provision.</p>
<p>Can the structure and format of updates be kept consistent?</p>	<p>Modelling centres are part of the Forcings TT, and this will help ensure that updates do not cause huge disruption. The TT has discussed the pros and cons of changing data formats. The intention would be to attempt, where possible, to bring the forcings more in line with the CF/CMIP data standards - do this once and then not change again. In theory, this should mean that the data are easier to manage (standard units across datasets, bounds, coordinates, data structure etc), but would require a one-off change to how these data are processed downstream (although it should greatly simplify downstream processing as the number of exceptions required should significantly decrease).</p>

Hunga-Tonga SPARC multi-MIP activity and specifically VolMIP will include both stratospheric water vapour and volcanic aerosols from volcanic eruptions. This mapping to individual ESM spectral wavebands will be additional dimension to volcanic forcings. On the stratospheric aerosol this is an emerging need in terms of Hunga Tonga due to dominant stratospheric water vapour forcing. Can this need be addressed?

2022 will be after the initial goal of updating until end of 2021 by mid-2024 so will need to wait for the next update in 2025. From a scientific perspective there is huge interest in exploring the response to Hunga-Tonga. Would be great to coordinate between the VolMIP forcings and the wider CMIP historical forcings. More discussion is required to determine how to best address this need.

Forcing TT members and stakeholders are involved in GloSSAC development which will provide link to the new international team on stratospheric aerosol observations and on the volcanic forcing datasets specifically, our Task Team (TT) has Thomas Aubry and Anja Schmidt as members. Discussions on inclusion of stratospheric water vapour are required.

Timeline and new requirements

Question

Answer

Regarding Hunga Tonga-Hunga Ha'apai (HTHH), will the CMIP7 volcanic forcings include a stratospheric water source, in addition to SO₂/aerosols?

We currently do not have a dedicated data provider for stratospheric water source from volcanoes on the TT. Discussions are ongoing on whether to provide recommendations for models who could handle a water vapour injection into the stratosphere, but not all models will be able to do this, and we would thus also need to create forcing files for other models which cannot be prioritized until we have a robust version of the aerosol product. If someone provides the data, it can be served on input4MIPs provided it meets the data formatting and testing requirements.

<p>Any discussion regarding potential ensemble of forcing datasets? Will there be alternative forcings available to help assess the impact of uncertainties in the historical forcings? Specifically solar, aerosols, land use etc.</p>	<p>Addressing forcing uncertainty was a core theme emphasized in survey responses. The TT membership is aware of interest in this research area (e.g., DAMIP, LESFMIP). Currently looking at the possibility and discussing the potential for creating an ensemble of some or all forcings although targeting a far longer timeframe. The core focus is our 2024 update delivery target. Uncertainty is certainly a hot topic by providers, analysts, and modellers.</p> <p>With input4MIPs we are open to collect additional datasets, if a provider is happy to meet the submission requirements.</p>
<p>What are the scenarios that will be considered in the CMIP7 forcing?</p>	<p>The Scenarios workshop (see https://wcrp-cmip.org/event/scenariomip-june23/) discussed the potential new scenario set for CMIP7. Several members of the Forcing TT were in attendance and will synthesize the current plans to the TT group, with a ScenarioMIP information webinar planned to share the outcomes of the workshop more widely.</p>

Plans for testing

<i>Question</i>	<i>Answer</i>
<p>Could summary statistics (e.g., timeseries of global emission totals) be provided together with the released datasets, so that modellers could confirm that they are ingesting these datasets correctly into their models?</p>	<p>Summary statistics are indeed very helpful for the modelling centres. The topic of testing approaches and outputs is an ongoing discussion in our Forcings TT documentation and tool development planning.</p>

Access, tools, documentation, and engagement

<i>Question</i>	<i>Answer</i>
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Will there be opportunities to feedback to those teams tasked with compiling specific datasets (e.g., ozone). Following CMIP5 and CMIP6 there have been issues which would have been better addressed following wider consultation with potential users. It would be great to have a more transparent structure in place to share lessons learned from previous CMIP cycles.

We hope the new structure that will be presented at the Forcings drop-in ([link to slides](#)), in addition to planned improvements in communication and development of new dedicated "one stop shop" webpages at wcrp-cmip.org will achieve exactly this goal! We are looking into ideas for more interactive feedback between data providers and users (e.g., mailing lists, Github, CVs/registry, webform, etc). In the meantime please send any feedback to cmip-ipo@esa.int or post a question to the [CMIP FAQs](#) and tag with the topic 'Forcings'.

On top of performing CMIP experiments, filling ES-Doc inquiries was another big burden for modelling groups. Are there any attempts going on to evaluate which parts of ES-Doc were absolutely necessary and which were not?

We are continuing a dialogue across all the technical Task Teams ([Data Citation](#), [Data Request](#), [Model Documentation](#), ..) about streamlining the information that we request from modelling groups with the Model Documentation Task Team leading on evolving and improving the ES-Doc.

Can forcing data sets documentation be mentioned or discussed? This is to enable better understanding of model data for improved evaluation and usage.

Definitely! The Forcings TT is addressing not only dataset documentation, but better clarity on how datasets have changed, and importantly, what forcing collection configuration a CMIP-contributed simulation used to support end users together with [Model Documentation Task Team](#) colleagues.

Requests for Forcings TT consideration

Inclusion of natural and anthropogenic sources in biomass burning datasets

It is a little difficult to separate what is "natural" and what is "anthropogenic", but for CH₄ etc, both can be quantified, with the CEDS dataset covering anthropogenic contributions. For the biomass burning (BB) these are a mix, what aspect of fire is anthropogenic and what is natural? There have also been ongoing conversations about how this would be done consistently when an ESM land surface scheme includes a fire sub-model, where there may be very different behaviour between forced and internally simulated biomass burning.

The inclusion of natural emissions of short-lived gases and aerosols, not available in CMIP6, has been discussed within the Forcings TT. At this moment, we do not have natural emissions data providers identified. If natural emissions data were used in CMIP6, it would be useful to collate the sources that were previously used and potential contacts that we could reach out to see if these can also be incorporated – the TT will aim to follow up on this.

Availability of code to transform the aerosol properties to optical properties

In the meeting there was discussion about a new stratospheric aerosol dataset. It was very nice to have the optical properties generated for us since it was done consistently for all models. However, after CMIP6 we found this forcing challenging to work with. The main reason being that there is a large number of zonal inputs (three optical properties for each wavelength interval). Our target model for CMIP7 will use rotated grids for which zonal mean input is problematic (it assumes all input is 3D). For the new dataset it would be good if code used to transform the aerosol properties to optics is available so modelling centres can decide if they want to read in the optics or compute them in their model.

The Forcing TT members include a number of modelling centres who will work closely with the forcing dataset provider to provide potential tools to support use. This cannot be promised due to potential funding and resource limitations. We hope that as datasets are developed and made available, a broad range of modelling groups will engage to test these. At this future point we welcome your feedback to ascertain if a solution could be developed that serves all future modelling group needs.

Separation of two solar irradiance products

In CMIP6, the official solar irradiance was the average of two separate products - it would have been better to keep them separate and allow for comparison.

This comment will feed into further TT discussions - the CMIP6 historical forcing dataset (see <https://solarisheppa.geomar.de/cmip6>) did attempt to account for radiative effects, and photochemical effects. As noted, having all of these data available so these could be adapted in the case that a model has interactive chemistry that accounts for one of the composite components would be useful indeed.

Dependency of the piControl forcings on full historical dataset

This dependency of the piControl forcings on the full historical dataset is unfortunate. Many modelling centres need finalized piControl forcings many months in advance of the final historical forcings since they need to spin up models for many centuries before starting a historical simulation.

As we noted the historical (starting in 1850) forcings first update is expected in 2024. This should facilitate testing, and if resultant simulations look good, then could be a prototype candidate for piControl use. It could work for the piControls to start in mid-2024 as long as the full timeseries (or at least 1850) is not updated again. The specification of volcanic forcing for piControl and the Scenarios has been flagged as problematic and is something that our new data providers are very keen on improving and will make recommendations. We understand the importance of freezing the 1850 piControl forcings as early as possible so that model spin up is complete in advance of the historical simulation to avoid dealing with piControl and historical simulations at the same time in addition to the stress of the looming timeline. The Forcings TT members will discuss and develop a plan to be shared with community. An additional TT aim is to coordinate with the PMIP community, as their past1000 experiment temporally overlaps with the piControl period. Thomas and Anja (Forcings TT member and stakeholder) are aware of this and are working across the broader community to ensure these connections are made.

5 Next steps

The Forcings TT co-leads, members and stakeholders thank all the participants for their input, wealth of feedback and insight provided during these drop-in sessions. The team meet regularly and will discuss many of the topics and issues raised while having a clear short-term focus on the delivery of updated/extended datasets to end of 2021 by mid-2024 and the wider [core goals](#) outlined during the session.

We will continue to prioritize regular opportunities for engagement and feedback. The Forcings TT, supported by the CMIP IPO, are developing "one stop shop" webpages on wcrp-cmip.org providing all CMIP forcings information and links to ease the user experience and support improved continuous feedback and engagement channels. Future drop-in sessions will also be planned at key times; for example, to launch the updated /extended datasets in mid-2024.

Widening global involvement and engagement in CMIP forcings activities is important. If you are a modelling centre that would like to run with preliminary forcings, please contact us and let us know when you might be ready. Having groups ready in early 2024 would be a great help. We are also particularly keen to widen global engagement and stakeholder opportunities for modelling centres e.g., there is currently no Asian modelling centre formally engaged and a very strong global North bias. If you are from these underrepresented groups, please do reach out.

Another area we are active in is looking to secure a more sustainable funding model for both forcing dataset development and potential to operationalise to realize the aspiration of regular and continuous data updates. This is a considerable challenge but the team together with the CMIP Panel, WIP and CMIP IPO have identified it as a priority to ensure that the difficulties faced due to forcing dataset delivery delays during CMIP6 are not repeated.

And finally...please do keep in touch! The team welcomes all input - add your question to the [CMIP FAQ](#) question submission form or email cmip-ipo@esa.int

6 Annex A – Raw data

CMIP Forcings drop in sessions - 7 June 2023

Capturing attendee questions and comments across both sessions (05:00 and 15:00 UTC). Participants are encouraged to agree (thumb up) or disagree (thumb down) with posts and to comment if they wish to. Participants can include their name against a point, but should be aware this might appear publicly in the future. The default is Anonymous.

CMIPIPO MAY 31, 2023 09:55AM UTC

TT goals

CMIP6 issues

New stratosphere aerosol dataset

(From Jason Cole, ECCC/CCCma)

In the meeting there was discussion about a new stratospheric aerosol dataset. It was very nice to have the optics generated for us since it was done consistently for all models. However, after CMIP6 we found this forcing a bit challenging to work with. The main reason being that there is a large number of zonal inputs (three optical properties for each wavelength interval). Our target model for CMIP7 will use rotated grids for which zonal mean input is problematic (it assumes all input is 3D).

For the new dataset it would be good if code used to transform the aerosol properties to optics is available so modelling centres can decide if want to read in the optics or compute them in their model.

Abrupt transitions in the mean or variability of certain emissions

There has been quite a few papers highlighting the unintended consequences of having abrupt transitions in the mean or variability of certain forcings in CMIP6 on the global climate. Will there be more of an effort to homogenize these forcing datasets (e.g., pre-satellite vs post-satellite observations, historical vs future scenarios) in CMIP7 to avoid these types of discontinuities?

natural emissions?

Will there be an attempt to specify natural emissions of short-lived gases and aerosols, unlike in CMIP6?

We have talked about that in the Forcing Task Team (TT). At this moment, we do not have natural emissions data providers identified. If natural emissions data were used in CMIP6, it would be useful to collate these sources and potential contacts that we could reach out to see if these can also be incorporated

– PAUL DURACK

Surely biomass burning datasets include natural and anthropogenic sources? – ANONYMOUS

It is a little difficult to separate what is "natural" and what is "anthropogenic", but for CH4 etc, both can be quantified, with CEDS covering the anthropogenic part. For the biomass burning (BB) these are a mix, what aspect of fire is anthropogenic and what is natural? There have also been ongoing conversations about how this would be done consistently when a land surface scheme includes a fire sub-model, where there may be very different behaviour between forced and internally simulated BB

– PAUL DURACK

Can we get access to beta versions of the forcing files for testing on an earlier timeline?

All data that has been validated through our testing will be available through <https://aims2.llnl.gov/search?project=input4MIPs> - as real-time as the data are available, and published under the "CMIP6Plus" mip era. We have our first PCMDI-AMIP-1-1-9 that was published last month, and expect the new data to be made available as they are finalized. Importantly, we want to collect and test, so expect that numerous releases of each dataset may occur as validation, testing and feedback is addressed – PAUL DURACK

I agree that it is very important that modeling groups get access to even preliminary versions of the forcings files, both to allow modeling centers to test their workflow for ingesting the forcings, and to identify any potential problems with the forcings ASAP.

– ANONYMOUS

That is the goal, with the first delivery date in 2024 (and updates thereafter, well before a potential CMIP7 timeline would begin

– PAUL DURACK

Ocean temperature biases in historical

Will the historical simulation be improved in terms of the biases in ocean temperature?

Some additional information would be useful - is the question related to CMIP6 forcing datasets? – PAUL DURACK

We should encourage both streams - updates using only time updates and new versions that redo the whole time series. – ANONYMOUS

Opportunities to feedback to providers?

Will there be opportunities to inform those teams tasked with compiling specific datasets (e.g. ozone). Following CMIP5 and CMIP6 there have been issues which would have been better addressed following wider consultation with potential users. It would be great to have a more transparent structure in place to share lessons learned from previous CMIP cycles.

We hope the new structure that will be presented at the forcings drop-in, in addition to better planned communication will achieve exactly this goal! – PAUL DURACK

Timeline and new requirements

Historical back to 1750?

Sorry that I couldn't make the drop-in sessions, so I might have missed this. Is there any information about whether the historical forcings will be extended back to 1750 for those groups who may want to try this? Thanks. Ed Hawkins

We discussed this in our task team as well as polled data providers in the survey to indicate the possibility to extend to 1750. Most datasets already extend back to 1750 (e.g., emissions, ghgs) and some new ones could be extended (e.g., volcanic SO2 emissions) but there are some that will not be extended (e.g., ozone) backwards in time. The general consensus was that this request could come as part of a focused MIP activity and will then be evaluated to see how much work is needed. – VAISHALI NAIK - NOAA FEDERAL

Thanks Vaishali! – ANONYMOUS

SLCF emissions

Vaishali's chart indicated many "updates" (rather than "extensions") for the SLCF emissions. Does this indicate that the whole historical timeseries will continue to change through 2026? If so, at what point will the "official" CMIP7 SLCF emissions be frozen? They can't continue to change once model simulations need to start.

The CEDS SLCF database is unique, in that it is constantly evolving. Whenever the data is written is the timestamp/version of the data, and even a week later, new observations may have been incorporated which means the timeseries would change. When we have a CMIP7 timeline, the forcing dataset collection will be set (just like we did in CMIP6), with no more "CMIP7" updates applied, unless of course issues are identified, which will be fixed, a new collection identified etc – PAUL DURACK

I would hope that once the CMIP7 "updates" are stopped, we might be able to continue to have CMIP7 "extensions" – ANONYMOUS

The idea of the "continuous DECK" is the motivation for the CMIP6Plus forcing collection (see [https://aims2.llnl.gov/search?project=input4MIPs&activeFacets={"mip_era":"CMIP6Plus"}](https://aims2.llnl.gov/search?project=input4MIPs&activeFacets={)), and I would hope, assuming that the forcing dataset providers are able to fund their activities, this could continue on an annual basis ongoing - wishful, but hopeful – PAUL DURACK

as long as the versioning is clear, continued updates are not a problem. – ANONYMOUS

With CEDS, we don't have an option. The only way that these data are available will be updates (full timeseries changes), so to prevent changes you'd be locked to a single version/timestamp – PAUL DURACK

IPCC timelines

Can someone (John?) comment on the constraints on the forcings timeline imposed by IPCC AR7 deadlines, to the extent that they are known?

The IPCC elections that will define the AR7 leadership are occurring 24 July (see <https://apps.ipcc.ch/fp/elections.php>). Once there is leadership in place, their first job will be to define a timeline. So at this point, we are in a waiting phase – PAUL DURACK

Volcanic forcing datasets for CMIP7-VolMIP experiment and alignment with HTHH impacts multi-MIP activity

Just to flag up the new multi-MIP activity aligned to a 2025 special report for the SPARC cross-activity project on Hunga-Tonga impacts.

This activity is aligned primarily to CCMI and ISA-MIP, and there are 3 specific experiments designed aligned to different timescale impacts from the eruption.

But from the splinter group meeting at EGU there are 2 new experiments proposed for CMIP7-VolMIP, 1 of which involves prescribing both volcanic aerosol and stratospheric water vapour forcings for phreato-plinian major eruption.

The forcing datasets for the multi-MIP activity then align also with this planned VolMIP experiment for CMIP7.

Sounds great. There are a number of post-CMIP6, pre-CMIP7 activities that are currently underway. If you haven't already, you may want to register your activity at <https://airtable.com/shryaY8sSLyLx7q2y>. On the volcanic forcing datasets specifically, our Task Team (TT) has Tom Aubrey and Anja Schmidt as members, and we are building on the work of Matt Toohey and Tom with their EVA and EVA_H packages, which will bring things more inline with CMIP6 VolMIP – PAUL DURACK

In regards to HTHH, will the CMIP7 volcanic forcings include a stratospheric water source, in addition to SO2/aerosols? – ANONYMOUS

@PaulDurack -- thanks, I'll add then to register this on the airtable link you've posted there. – ANONYMOUS

Both @anja & myself are members of the ISSI team on "Perspectives on stratospheric aerosol observations", and @thomas was at the EGU splinter group meeting. And now that the multi-MIP activity is crystallised to specific experiments I'll contact them both to discuss. — ANONYMOUS

In reply to the question about whether a stratospheric water source, in addition to SO₂/aerosols. No, the idea is not to simulate the volcanic water interactively (at least not within VolMIP), but to provide a 2nd forcing dataset, for the volcanic SWV forcing. — ANONYMOUS

Will there be alternative forcings be available to help assess the impact of uncertainties in the historical forcings? Specifically solar, aerosols, land use etc.

Very good idea! With input4MIPs we are open to collect additional datasets, if a provider is happy to meet the submission requirements. YES PLEASE! — PAUL DURACK

In CMIP6, the official solar irradiance was the average of two separate products - it would have been better to keep them separate and allow folks that wanted to compare them. — ANONYMOUS

Good suggestion, we can feed that comment into ongoing TT discussions - the CMIP6 historical forcing dataset (see <https://solarisheppa.geomar.de/cmip6>) did attempt to account radiative effects, and photochemical effects. As you note having all of these data available so these could be adapted in the case that a model has interactive chemistry that accounts for a component would be useful indeed. — PAUL DURACK

timeline for PiControl forcing

I just wanted to know whether it is already clear by when we will have a PiControl forcing available. Will piControl forcing simply be derived from the 1850 historical forcing, and therefore piControl is defined (and from then on kept unchanged) once the historical forcing is defined? I ask as community MIPs' simulation designs may depend on details of the piControl forcing. For PMIP, for example, this dependence is very strong.

The piControl forcings are part of the DECK (and historical) forcing dataset delivery, which we expect in early 2024 (extended to 2021). Once these forcings are in place, we can revisit the experimental design protocol for piControl, in addition to interacting with PMIP colleagues to work toward consistency between the paleo and 1850- connection — PAUL DURACK

In the case of some forcings (e.g., solar, volcanic), I assume that the piControl forcings will not be simply the 1850 historical values, but rather some sort of multi-year mean. — ANONYMOUS

Correct, the experimental design for CMIP6 was climatological values for the piControl (volcanic, average over 1850–2014 - see https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/input4mips/?institution_id=IACETH, and solar, average over 185001–187301 - see https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/input4mips/?institution_id=SOLARIS-HEPPA), which we may want to revisit once we have the next-gen forcings available, as we received some comments through the surveys about the CMIP6 piControl climatological volcanic forcing specification — PAUL DURACK

This dependency of the piControl forcings on the full historical dataset is unfortunate. Many modeling centers need finalized piControl forcings many months in advance of the final historical forcings, since they need to spin up models for many centuries before starting a historical simulation. — ANONYMOUS

As we noted the historical (starting in 1850) forcings first update is expected in 2024. This should facilitate testing, and if resultant simulations look good, then could be a prototype candidate for piControl use — PAUL DURACK

I will also add that the specification of volcanic forcing for piControl and the Scenarios has been flagged as problematic and is something that our new data providers are very keen on improving. As a modeler, I also agree that it is important to freeze the 1850 PiControl forcings as early as possible so that model spin up is complete in advance of the historical simulation. We don't want to be dealing with piControl and historical simulations at the same time in addition to the stress of the looming timeline. That said, I agree with the Paul that the first update of the full forcing timeseries is unlikely early-mid 2024, which could work for the piControls to start in mid 2024 as long as the full timeseries (or at least 1850) is not updated again. We will discuss this with our TT members and come up with a plan. — VAISHALI NAIK - NOAA FEDERAL

On volcanic forcing in piControl and ScenarioMIP, I'd also question whether 1850–present is the right baseline as opposed to say 850–1850. Not that many large eruptions in the historical period (average SO₂ flux twice lower for 1850–present vs 850–1850) so it might bias a bit the piControl and Scenario towards a low volcanic forcing baseline. Defo something to be discussed as a community. (Thomas Aubry) — ANONYMOUS

Scenarios

What are the scenarios that will be considered in the CMIP7 forcing?

The Scenarios workshop (see <https://wcrp-cmip.org/event/scenariomip-june23/>) will discuss exactly this question — PAUL DURACK

Potential to operationalise and produce annual updates?

To what extent is it now possible to operationalize the production of historical forcing data so that it is updated every year? This encompasses two classes of updates - single additional years that are continuous with the existing timeseries, and also larger revisions that would periodically update an entire timeseries as a function of changing assumptions or new data. The impacts of COVID, or other unforeseen events (large biomass burning, volcanic eruptions, solar cycle updates, marine shipping emission cuts etc.) need to be assessed on timescales that are much shorter than the typical CMIP cycle.

We hope that the planning that will be described in the forcings drop-in, along with our near-term and longer-term timelines will answer this question. A challenge is that currently forcing dataset providers in most cases are not specifically supported to produce these datasets. So we will need to determine a way to ensure adequate support is identified for this very important contribution to the CMIP project — PAUL DURACK

Additionally, the workflow and data dependencies vary for the forcings which means that there would be diversity in the definition of "real time". Some forcings may be updated/produced on an annual basis (e.g., GHGs) while others may not (e.g., land-use). It would be important to identify such dependencies and barriers to operational production of forcings. – ANONYMOUS

Plans for testing

Summary statistics

Could summary statistics (e.g., timeseries of global emission totals) be provided together with the released datasets, so that modelers could confirm that they are ingesting these datasets correctly into their models?

We have actively been thinking about what tests, and what summaries would be useful, some of these are already publicly available (see <https://github.com/JGCRI/CEDS/tree/master/documentation>). It would be useful to coordinate, and communicate these resources – and definitely something that is on the to-do list. If you have examples, or better code! that does some of this evaluation, it would be great to collate this – PAUL DURACK

Access, tools, documentation and engagement

Forcing dataset documentation

Can forcing data sets documentation be mentioned or discussed? This is to enable better understanding of model data for improved evaluation and usage.

Couldn't agree more, not only dataset documentation, but better clarity on how datasets changed, and importantly, what forcing collection configuration a CMIP-contributed simulation used – PAUL DURACK

Other comments

Format stability

For the new datasets, it would be useful to try to maintain stability in the file format as new ones are provided in 2024 time-period and then updated. This would allow modelling centers to make a one-time switch to the new format early and then confidently and quickly pull in updates.

Completely agree Jason (Cole, CCCma). We have the CMIP data standards (single variable per file, CF standard names, etc), and where it makes sense reformatting the forcing to as closely as possible align to that would aid their evaluation and use – PAUL DURACK

Streamlining ES-Doc

On top of performing CMIP experiments, filling ES-Doc inquiries was another big burden for modeling groups. Are there any attempts going on to evaluate which part of ES-Doc was really necessary and which was not? We are of course willing to collaborate.

(Michio) – ANONYMOUS

The Model documentation task team is working on this <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip7-task-teams/model-documentation/> – CMIPPO

Thanks Michio, we are continuing a dialogue across all the technical Task Teams (citation, data request, model doc, ..) about streamlining the information that we request from modelling groups, so that we ask once, use many more times than once, in addition to having a centralized source of core information, ala an augmented https://github.com/WCRP-CMIP/CMIP6_CVs/ – PAUL DURACK

Thank you for your responses. I am a member of the data request TT so looking forward to the interactions. (Michio) – ANONYMOUS
